

Explanation of Nationalism Feelings in the Creation of Novels

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Abstract. *The work of the progressive Mahmudhodji Behbudi was studied in the article. Behbudi was open in his home and taught the country for free. He used educational methods in the field of education in the educational system. It is studied to teach Turkish children, to give them practical advice, and to give them practical advice in their dress and gait.*

Key words: *nationalism, patriotism, education, national, education, method, Turkestan, youth, military service, development, reform, knowledge, education, children.*

In Behbudi's work, patriotism is a whole concept, which is the sum of the human and spiritual values of the nation in Turkestan.

We see that Behbudi performed his services to the Motherland, the nation and the youth with true devotion. His services to the youth in this regard are incomparable. It is the goal of the progressive youth that they should learn science for the future, to become children of the nation loyal to the motherland. As mentioned in his article "Our deeds are our will", "Fathers of Akshaya should not be excited about the education of a child, just as they are not excited about weddings and marakas".[1]

Behbudi shows the methods of raising children in the country. In the first place, he himself tried to make disciples. He provided spiritual and economic support to his students. Makhmudhoja Behbudi considered that educating the children of Turkestan is the first priority. He also paid great attention to the teacher and disciple. This enlightened person made it possible for gifted children to go and study in countries such as Turkey and Egypt, which have developed at their own expense. Abdusalam Azimi, one of Behbudi's students who received fatherly care, wrote remembering what his teacher said before his trip to Turkey: "You should go to Bayazid Student Society in Istanbul as I showed you. Please deliver my greetings and letter from Effendi Gasprinsky there. Then the society will show you the place of service and after you are released from the service, they will explain to you the education in Egypt and give you help and advice in every way. After I sent the address, he promised that he would send the tuition fees continuously, and gave letters of recommendation to Bogchasaroy, Sevastopol and Istanbul" [2].

In the course of his memoirs, Abdusalam Azimi writes in detail about how he went to Bogchasaray and met with Gasprali, then took letters of recommendation from Turkey and left for Egypt, and about the economic and spiritual support given to him by his teacher Behbudi during his studies. At the same time when there is a struggle between old and new schools, it is necessary to make students like Abdusalam Azimi knowledgeable and knowledgeable.

Behbudi wants the children of the nation to work for the development of their people, to keep up with the times, and to pay special attention to science and enlightenment. In the thinker's view, science is the basis of patriotism. If in the article "How Nations Develop": "The ulama of the developing nations are aware of the times and strive for the "modernity of the nation" and donate to the rich people of the nation with modesty and admiration. invites, incites and provokes. In conclusion, the ulama of

every nation, the people of the nation write for the nation, the writer and the airman express the nation and the modernity to the belonging of their nation"[3], the article "Patriotism is needed" calls the youth of the nation to be patriotic. Behbudi's appeal to patriotism is the basis of instilling the sense of patriotism in young people. Behbudi describes the processes taking place in European countries so that the youth of the nation understand what the Motherland is. Lands in Russia, Germany, Belgium, Austria, England, their location, the size of their areas, and the scientific basis of their distance to Turkestan are of interest to the reader. By showing the achievements of other countries, it instills in young people love for their own country. As Behbudi himself wrote: "Our goal was to encourage the patriotism of Turkestan Muslims." The author writes that "We should express our patriotism because of the announcement of the enemy to our country." And express patriotism is to donate to the state with money and property. It is also necessary to refrain from actions and words that disturb the public opinion. Horses and carts and supplies should be easily provided to the government when needed. However, the government can give money. In some countries, the government takes something from the people during the war" [4].

Behbudi called on the youth of Turkestan for patriotism, and when there is a war in the world and against the homeland, patriotism is definitely needed. This kind of patriotism consists in the fact that, at the same time, economic and material support is given to the state. Moreover, in order to protect the homeland, it is necessary to protect the people from ways that touch their feelings, divert them to other ways, and break their words.

It should be noted that Behbudi promotes nationalism in many of his articles. He appreciates the achievements of other nations, respects their science. He also wants the Russian state, its people and the nations of other countries to be peaceful and pray for their victory. "The purpose of writing this is that our brothers from Turkestan should not be disturbed, but should go about their business with perfect peace, pray for the victory of the Russian motherland, and be loyal to the government in every possible way. let them obey. And if they didn't listen to the words that he ran away."

In Behbudi, we see that nationalism is formed in harmony with the feelings of patriotism. That is, in his works, love of the nation in a broad sense reflects the principle of love for the homeland. There is no country without the nation and its development.

Taraqiyarparvar's article "Address to Dear Youth" [5] is also one of the main articles aimed at educating young people in the spirit of patriotism and nationalism. Behbudi says that, first of all, schools are the first foundation of development in the country. The author says that they are: - masterpieces of culture and happiness. To the youth of the nation: "The nation will not enter the path of progress and use culture until it first of all reforms and increases the primitiveness of the alphabet. A nation that is not armed with the weapons of education will not see the face of pleasure and happiness in the world, it will be completely defeated in the field of "life in the field of struggle" and will be crushed under the feet" [5].

Secondly, Behbudi emphasized that attention should be paid to the primary education of the children of the nation. He wanted to establish new modern schools and pay attention to discipline and education in them. Also, Behbudi assigns tasks to the youth, saying: "they will raise children in a perfect manner in the national and religious spirit."

Thirdly, Behbudi was concerned about the dearth in education. "Currently, there are few teachers in Turkestan, and our need for teachers is dire." He raised the issue of opening hundreds of schools in the country and increasing the number of teachers in Turkestan. As the thinker himself said: "The youth of Turkestan must find a way to get a teacher."

Fourthly, Behbudi put forward the idea that enlightenment saves ignorance, and assigned the task of introducing short teacher training courses to our youth. He expressed confidence that such courses were organized by Munavvarqori in Tashkent and that he would accept them with pleasure and that the result would be good.

Behbudi has high hopes for the youth of Turkestan. In his article "The statement of truth"[6], the goal is set from the very beginning of the appeal: "It is necessary to know: "Rights are taken, not given!".

That is, a fee will be charged, and no one will give it to you. Therefore, he called on the youth and all intellectuals and progressives to unite for the development of the country. In addition, he encouraged the rich and scholars to join him on this path. He also called everyone for autonomous freedom around the political society. He especially wants young people to serve the people and the nation: "Young people want to serve the nation and the masses of the people. Their fault is that they are narrow inside. We have a lot of work ahead of us. Other nations are progressing every minute. I repeat that young and old should work together. However, neither freedom nor autonomy will be given to us. After all, these blessings are given to each nation according to its readiness" [6]. Therefore, Behbudi urges the youth to fight for the truth and worry about the future of the nation. But he says: "The current discord of our people saddens me. Woe to us when other nations work in alliance, and we are enemies with each other. inculcated the idea that it is necessary to go to autonomy.

Behbudi's views on the history of the homeland stand out. These views of his lead to educate our youth in the spirit of patriotism and nationalism. His "The history of Turkistan is needed", "History and geography", "The word Sart was not known", "Duma and Turkestan", "We need four languages, not two", "The time of education and travel" and food" are among them dozens of articles.

The article "Education and travel time and food" is one of the main works that promote patriotism and nationalism to the children of Turkestan. It should be said that Behbudi is distinguished by his use of the Holy Qur'an and hadiths in calling the youth and the people of our country to education and upbringing. Because he is a religious figure, he makes extensive use of religious education. For example: "Allimu avladakum li zaman ghairi zamandikum, liannahum huliqu li zaman ghairi zamanikum". That is: "O Muslims! Teach your children the science of the coming time! Because God Almighty made them a people, other than your time, that is, for the coming time" [7]. It can be seen that Behbudi is very skilled when he uses the phrase "the science of the coming age" and "for the coming age". That is, every child of the country is encouraged to receive upbringing and education for the future and in accordance with the future. In other words, he reinforces his opinion with the rules of Sharia saying that "the demand of every Muslim for a husband and a wife is obligatory knowledge". It is said that you learned science even if you went to China. This was his fertilizer for the representatives of the nation to come. That is, the coming time will remind you that you are a child of a scientific, progressive, developing country. Kelar wants to be a nation that is educated in accordance with the times.

Behbudi promoted higher education along with the new method of school education. He made many speeches in this regard at the same time. For example, in the "Oyina" magazine: "It is known to open-minded people that there is a need to reform the methodical education of schools and madrasas. Modern science should be religious and modern. It is necessary to study science of medicine and science of wisdom. Science, profession and industry are also obligatory. Profession is obligatory. Knowing the science of every fard is also fard. The world of science always progresses with effort and experience." [8]. Also, as we mentioned above, he encouraged young people to learn foreign languages. In his article entitled "Not two, four languages are necessary"[9], he urged the children of the country to learn languages.

Behbudi's views on patriotism and nationalism are still valid today. In his articles, the problems of economic backwardness and lack of economic culture are addressed. Behbudi writes about frugality and extravagance with regret and regret. He calls the people of the country to be thrifty. Rich people who are rich and do not educate their son are criticized. In his works, child education is embodied as the future of the nation. The essence of the socio-political movement of the Jadis, founded by Behbudi, became of great importance. The whole country of Turkestan followed him, even when they followed, they did not join these actions by force, they followed because of his new reforms. In addition, he fought for the fate of the nation and the homeland. His activity and creativity became an example as a historical school.

Behbudi's efforts to enlighten the nation and to form the country's youth as patriots became a school for our youth. His painstaking actions, hard ways, sacrifices for the nation are an example of patriotism for our youth. Today's young people should know, study, remember, promote and encourage such a patriot, the founder of the nation, a great intellectual figure.

Behbudi's true patriot and nationalistic humanity is seen again in his promotion of books, reading culture and establishment of a library. We know that he has a high level of knowledge in his work, as a theoretician and practitioner in the field of spreading enlightenment. In addition, he is one of the founders of the practice of information distribution. Behbudi published in the press bodies, i.e. "Samarkand" newspaper (1913); In addition to interesting articles, "Oyina" magazine also published announcements in Uzbek, Russian, and Persian. His announcements reached the Caucasus, Tatarstan, Iran, Afghanistan, India, and Turkey mainly through the "Oyina" magazine.

Therefore, the "Behbudi Library", which can be evaluated as a historical event in the cultural life of Behbudi region, was a great event in the life of our youth and the nation. In 1914, the enlightener published an article in the "Oyina" magazine under the title "Behbudiya library"[10]. It says: permission was obtained from the government to open a library in the name of "Behbudiya Library". In the library, all types of ancient and modern Arabic, Persian, Turkish and Farangi books, scientific and scientific maps and tools, which have been published in Russia and abroad, have passed the censorship, are collected and sold in bulk at a low price. The city of Behbudiya Library opens in the office of the weekly "Oyina" magazine in Samarkand, Russia, in the room of the publisher and editor of "Oyina" and the owner of Behbudiya Library, Mahmudhoja Behbudiya.

Mahmudhoja was Behbudi's idea. Also, in connection with the opening of the library, in addition to the sale of books published in Russia and abroad, the acceptance of various books from the population on a commission basis was a great practical event. "Kutubkhonai Behbudiya" created by Mahmudhoja Behbudi, according to the amount of rare books, bibliography and library science resources collected in it, it became clear to everyone that it is the largest library in Turonzamin after his death.

Behbudi's actions in the field of school and education, reading and teaching, as well as the establishment of a library are examples for our youth today. As Behbudi said: "worldly science and knowledge are necessary to survive in the world, a nation without knowledge and science will be trampled on by other nations."

References:

1. M. Behbudi. Our actions are clear. Selected works. - Tashkent: "Spirituality", 2020. - P.160-161.
2. Azimi A. My memories and impressions about Beh Budi . - "Zarafshon" newspaper, March 25, 1923.
3. Behbudi. How nations progress. Selected works. - T.: "Spirituality", - B. 389-390.
4. Behbudi. Patriotism is needed. Selected works. The first volume. - T.: "Akademnashr", 2018. - B. 443-444.
5. Behbudi. Address to young people. Selected works. The first volume. - T.: "Akademnashr", 2018. - B. 443-444.
6. Behbudi. The statement is true. Selected works. The first volume. - T.: "Akademnashr", 2018. - B. 474-476.
7. Behbudi. Study and travel time and food. Selected works. The second volume. - T.: "Akademnashr", 2018. - B. 55.
8. Behbudi. Students need help. Selected works. The first volume. - T.: "Akademnashr", 2018. - B. 434-436.
9. Behbudi. Four languages are needed, not two. Selected works. The first volume. - T.: "Akademnashr", 2018. - B. 396-398.